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Intellectual Capital And Fair Value Of Listed Industrial Goods Firms In Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria and likewise in many other countries around the globe, it is observed that firms depend to a considerable extent on their intellectual capital to sharpen their competitive edge. The main objective of this study was to examine the relationship between intellectual capital and fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The study adopted an *ex-post facto* research design and utilized a panel data of ninety (90) pooled observations gathered from nine (9) listed industrial goods firms over ten (10)-year period (2015-2024). The study however employed a panel multiple regression technique to analyze the data via E-views 10.0 statistical package. The study findings revealed that there is significant positive relationship between human capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 1.280405{0.0001}) of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria, there is a significant positive relationship between structural capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 4.128763{0.0000}) of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria, there is a significant positive relationship between relational capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 0.529721 {0.0025}) of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria, there is a positive non-significant relationship between innovation capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 2.259483{0.0668}) of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria while there is a negative non-significant relationship between process capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = -0.0271887{0.0893}) of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria. It was thus concluded that intellectual capital has a significant effect on fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The recommendations made included that industrial goods firms in Nigeria should prioritize investments in human capital development, such as training and development programs, talent acquisition and retention, and employee empowerment to enhance their competitiveness and fair value.

Keywords: intellectual capital, employee empowerment,

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria and likewise in many other countries around the globe, it is observed that firms depend to a considerable extent on their intellectual capital to sharpen their competitive edge (Onyekwelu & Okoh, 2017). According to Duho and Agomor (2021), intellectual capital refers to those non-physical assets that can be converted into values and the aggregation of all knowledge and competences of employees that help an organization to achieve competitive advantage. The widespread acceptance of intellectual capital as a source of competitive advantage led to the development of appropriate methods of its measurement. Retaining highly skilled and knowledgeable employees is crucial for sustained innovation and company growth. High turnover rates can disrupt operations, erode the firm's intellectual capital, and result in the loss of expertise. This can lead to decreased productivity, reduced competitiveness, and ultimately a lower fair value. The success of any business entity rest upon its ability to adopt a well-organized intellectual

capital system as opined by Akpan and Akinniyi (2019). The intellectual capital of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria plays a crucial role in determining their fair value. A strong brand can attract loyal customers, maintain pricing power, and generate higher revenues. It also provides a competitive edge over competitors, enhancing the firm's fair value. Firms with huge intellectual capital potentials are perceived as having a stronger potential for future revenue streams, which positively impacts their fair value (Ukpe et.al, 2024).

The reputation of an industrial goods firm's brand is a valuable intangible asset which may contribute significantly to its fair value. Human capital is a significant component of intellectual capital, but turnover and talent retention challenges can negatively impact a firm's value (Emenyi, 2024¹). Industrial goods firms that have long-standing relationships with customers, built on trust and reliability, possess valuable intellectual capital. These relationships often lead to repeat business, customer loyalty, and positive word-of-mouth referrals. Such factors strengthen the firm's fair value by ensuring a stable revenue stream. Effective supply chain management, including strategic partnerships and efficient logistics, can enhance an industrial goods firm's intellectual capital (John et al., 2018). Well-managed supply chains ensure reliable access to raw materials, timely delivery to customers, and cost savings. These intellectual capital potentials or factors improve firms' operational efficiency and competitiveness, thereby positively affecting its fair value. Isola et al., (2017), stated that while intellectual capital is an important determinant of firm value in Nigeria, its specific impact may vary based on the company's industry position, market conditions, management effectiveness, and the overall quality and utilization of intellectual assets (Emenyi, 2024²).

1.2 Statement of the problem

In recent years, companies especially those in the industrial goods sector, have experienced a dynamic and competitive environment as opined by Eka et al., (2019). The problem that confronts businesses, users of accounting information, standard setters and regulators is how to best understand and communicate the difference between the value of a company, usually expressed as market prices of their shares and the accounting book value of that company (Idigo, 2023). Competition at a cross-border scale compels domestic companies to adjust their competitive position by achieving sustainable fair value. Intellectual capital, which encompasses intangible assets and human capital amongst others can have both positive and negative aspects in relation to the fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

The value of intangible assets like patents, trademarks, or copyrights can be subject to fluctuations in the market. Changes in consumer preferences, technological advancements, or regulatory developments can render certain intangible assets less valuable or even obsolete (Nnubia et al., 2019). This can lead to a decrease in the fair value of a firm if its intangible assets are not being effectively utilized or if they become devalued. Intangible assets often lack tangible collateral, unlike physical assets such as machinery or real estate. This abnormality can make it more difficult for industrial goods firms to secure loans or access additional funding based solely on their intellectual capital. Lenders may be hesitant to provide financing without tangible assets as collateral, which could limit the firm's ability to raise capital and potentially impact its fair value.

A plethora of studies relating to intellectual capital, its effect and relationship with series of performance metrics abound in the literature. However, majority of the findings and judgments gained are inconsistent in their outcomes and conclusions. Some empirical facts (for instance, Idigo, 2023; Adesanmi, 2021; Muhammad *et al.*, 2020; Nnubia et al., 2019; Okenwa et al., 2017; Onyekwelu et al., 2017) documented a positive significant relationship. Other studies such as Akpan and Akinniyi (2019) suggested an insignificant positive relationship. Surprisingly, Duho and Agomor (2021) alongside Onyekwelu and Ubesie, (2016) recorded an inverse nexus. None of these studies reviewed dealt on fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. In view of the above, this study aimed at ascertaining the relationship between intellectual capital and fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria which is the gap. Human capital, structural capital, relational capital, innovation capital and process capital are the explanatory variables while fair value is represented by price-to-book value respectively.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to examine the relationship between intellectual capital and fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. However, the specific objectives was to:

1. Determine the relationship between Human capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the relationship between Structural capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
3. Assess the relationship between Relational capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
4. Examine the relationship between Innovation capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
5. Evaluate the relationship between process capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

1.4 Research questions

This study provide reliable answers to the following questions;

1. What is the relationship between Human capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria?
2. To what extent does structural capital relate with price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria?
3. How does relational capital relate with price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria?
4. To what extent does innovation capital relate with price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria?
5. What magnitude of effect does process capital have on price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual framework

2.1.1 Intellectual capital

Intellectual capital refers to the intangible assets and resources that contribute to the competitive advantage and value creation of a company. These assets are not physical in nature but include knowledge, expertise, innovations, patents, trademarks, brand reputation, customer relationships, and organizational processes. Intellectual capital plays a vital role in driving innovation, growth, and sustainability. Intellectual capital also relates to the ability to innovate and develop new products, processes, and technologies (Setyewati et.al., 2019). Listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria need to invest in research and development activities to stay competitive, meet changing customer needs, and address market demands. This includes developing patented technologies, improving existing products, and exploring new market opportunities. Overall, intellectual capital in the context of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria encompasses a wide range of intangible assets that contribute to their competitive advantage, profitability, fair value and long-term success. Effectively leveraging and managing intellectual capital is essential for these firms to thrive in a rapidly evolving business environment and maintain their position in the market as suggested by Apiti et al., (2017).

2.1.2 Human capital

Human capital is a crucial element of intellectual capital that significantly impacts the fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Human capital refers to the knowledge, skills, expertise, experience, creativity, and capabilities of individuals within an organization. It represents the collective talent, competencies, and potential of employees that drive value creation, innovation, and organizational performance (Aluwong, 2022). In the phase of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, human capital plays a pivotal role in shaping the firm's fair value through various dimensions. Employees are not merely resources but valuable assets that contribute to the competitive advantage and sustainable growth of the

organization. Their intellectual abilities, specialized skills, and domain knowledge are essential for operational excellence, product development, customer relations, risk management, and overall strategic decision-making.

Through human capital, listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria can enhance their innovative capacity by leveraging employees' creativity, problem-solving skills, and industry expertise to develop new products, processes, and technologies that cater to market demands and preferences. This ability to innovate and adapt to changing market conditions is crucial for maintaining competitiveness, driving revenue growth, and enhancing the firm's fair value.

2.1.3 Structural capital

Structural capital is a critical component of intellectual capital that plays a significant role in shaping the fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Structural capital refers to the infrastructure, systems, processes, technologies, databases, patents, trademarks, and other intangible assets that support and enhance the operations, innovation, and strategic capabilities of an organization (Hamdan, 2018). Within the phase of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, structural capital contributes to the firm's fair value by providing a framework for knowledge creation, sharing, and utilization across the organization. It encompasses the organizational structure, policies, procedures, and information systems that facilitate efficient communication, collaboration, and coordination among employees, departments, and business units (Chiucchi et al., 2018).

Structural capital enables listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria to leverage their collective knowledge, expertise, and resources effectively to drive operational excellence, innovation, and value creation as opined by Nawaz and Haniffa (2017). By establishing standardized processes, best practices, and quality management systems, organizations can streamline operations, minimize errors, reduce inefficiencies, and enhance productivity, leading to cost savings and improved financial performance. Onyekwelu et al., (2017) x-rayed that structural capital supports innovation and creativity within the organization by fostering a conducive environment for idea generation, experimentation, and knowledge sharing. Through investments in research and development, technology infrastructure, and intellectual property rights, firms can develop new products, processes, and services that differentiate them from competitors, meet market demands, and sustain long-term growth, thereby increasing their fair value. Additionally, structural capital plays a crucial role in risk management and compliance by ensuring that the organization has robust governance structures, internal controls, and legal frameworks in place to mitigate risks, safeguard assets, and adhere to regulatory requirements as stated by Adesanmi, (2021). By maintaining transparent reporting mechanisms, data security protocols, and ethical standards, firms can build trust with investors, customers, and other stakeholders, thereby enhancing their reputation and fair value in the market (Aluwong, 2022). Furthermore, structural capital contributes to customer relationships and loyalty by enabling firms to capture, organize, and leverage customer data, feedback, and insights to personalize offerings, anticipate needs, and deliver tailored solutions that enhance customer satisfaction and retention.

2.1.4 Relational capital

Relational capital is a key component of intellectual capital that plays a crucial role in shaping the fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Relational capital refers to the relationships, networks, and partnerships that an organization has developed with its stakeholders, including customers, suppliers, investors, employees, regulators, and the community at large. Within the context of intellectual capital and fair value, relational capital focuses on the intangible assets arising from strong, trust-based connections forged with external parties. These relationships are built on mutual understanding, goodwill, reputation, and shared values, leading to collaborative opportunities, knowledge exchanges, and value co-creation that benefit both the firm and its stakeholders. Listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria leverage relational capital to enhance their fair value in several ways. Firstly, by cultivating strong relationships with customers through exceptional service, personalized experiences, and efficient communication, organizations can foster loyalty, repeat business, and positive word-of-mouth referrals, ultimately increasing customer lifetime value and market share (Aluwong, 2022).

Secondly, relational capital plays a vital role in supplier partnerships, enabling firms to secure reliable sources of raw materials, components, and services, negotiate favorable terms, and drive operational efficiency in the supply chain (Araniyar & Chizea, 2017). By establishing trust-based relationships with suppliers based on transparency, fairness, and collaboration, organizations can minimize supply chain disruptions, reduce costs, and improve product quality, all of which contribute to enhancing their fair value (Araniyar & Chizea, 2017). According to Buallay, (2017) relational capital extends to investor relations, where listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria engage with shareholders, analysts, and financial institutions to communicate their strategic vision, performance metrics, and growth prospects. By maintaining open lines of communication, providing timely and accurate financial information, and demonstrating corporate governance best practices, organizations can build investor confidence, attract capital investment, and support a higher valuation in the market. Furthermore, relational capital encompasses employee relationships, focusing on creating a positive work environment, fostering a culture of trust and respect, and empowering staff to contribute their skills, knowledge, and creativity to the organization. Chang and Lee, (2012) postulated that investing in employee development programs, recognition initiatives, and diversity and inclusion practices, firms can improve employee engagement, retention, and productivity, leading to enhanced organizational performance and fair value.

2.1.5 Innovation capital

Innovation capital is a concept that encompasses the value derived from an organization's ability to innovate, create, and implement new ideas, products, processes, or ways of doing business. It represents the intangible assets and capabilities that enable a company to generate and capitalize on innovation opportunities, driving growth, competitiveness, and sustainability in today's dynamic business environment. At its core, innovation capital emphasizes a strategic approach to innovation that goes beyond just generating novel ideas but also focuses on effectively managing the innovation process, fostering a culture of creativity and experimentation, and leveraging technological advancements and market insights to deliver value to customers and stakeholders (Akpan & Akinniyi, 2019). Nassar, (2018) provided that organizations with high innovation capital are characterized by a culture of continuous learning, adaptation, and collaboration that encourages employees at all levels to think creatively, challenge the status quo, and pursue innovative solutions to complex problems. They invest in research and development, technology infrastructure, and talent development to build a robust innovation ecosystem that supports idea generation, validation, prototyping, and commercialization (Anifowose et al., 2017).

Innovation capital is not only about having a pipeline of new products or services but also about cultivating a mindset of innovation across the organization, where risk-taking, failure tolerance, and knowledge-sharing are encouraged and rewarded. It involves aligning innovation initiatives with strategic goals, customer needs, and market trends to ensure that the innovations produced create tangible value and differentiation in the marketplace (Anifowose et al., 2017). Furthermore, innovation capital extends beyond the internal capabilities of an organization to encompass external partnerships, collaborations, and ecosystems that can amplify and accelerate innovation outcomes. By engaging with external stakeholders such as customers, suppliers, research institutions, start-ups and industry experts, organizations can access diverse perspectives, expertise, and resources that complement their internal competencies and fuel innovation efforts.

2.1.6 Process capital

Process capital refers to the organizational processes, systems, and procedures that enable a company to create value and achieve its goals. It encompasses the documented and undocumented knowledge, practices, and routines that are embedded in the organization's workflows, operations, and activities. Effective process capital is critical to a company's success, as it enables the organization to streamline operations, reduce waste, improve efficiency, and increase productivity. Yusliza et al., (2020) stated that by having well-designed processes in place, companies can ensure consistency in the quality of their products or services, improve customer satisfaction, and build a strong reputation in the market.

Process capital is a valuable asset that can drive business growth and competitiveness. It enables companies to innovate and improve continuously, identify areas for improvement, and develop new products and services. Process capital also facilitates knowledge sharing and transfer within the organization, allowing employees to learn from each other's experiences and expertise (Eka et al., 2019). Moreover, process capital can be a key differentiator for companies, setting them apart from their competitors and enabling them to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage. Duho, (2022) postulated that by investing in process capital, companies can improve their overall performance, increase efficiency, and enhance their competitiveness in the market. The importance of process capital lies in its ability to support the delivery of products and services, drive innovation, and facilitate knowledge sharing. Companies that prioritize process capital are better equipped to adapt to changing market conditions, respond to customer needs, and stay ahead of the competition (Chen et al., 2005). Documenting and standardizing processes, companies can reduce errors, improve quality, and increase productivity as reviewed by Dohu and Agomor, (2022). Furthermore, process capital can be leveraged to drive business growth, improve customer satisfaction, and increase profitability. Process capital is a critical component of intellectual capital that can have a significant impact on a company's success and competitiveness (Eka et al., 2019).

2.1.7 Fair value

The concept of fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria refers to the estimated worth or valuation of these companies based on objective and transparent criteria. The fair value represents the price at which an asset or company would be exchanged between knowledgeable, willing parties in an open market transaction (Handam, 2018). Determining the fair value of listed industrial goods firms involves considering various factors such as the company's financial performance, assets, liabilities, market conditions, industry outlook, and potential for future growth. This valuation approach takes into account both quantitative and qualitative factors to arrive at a reasonable estimate of the firm's value. In Nigeria, the fair value of listed industrial goods firms is often assessed through different matrices such as price-to-earnings (P/E) ratio, price-to-sales (P/S) ratio, and price-to-book (P/B) ratio, to determine if the company is overvalued or undervalued relative to its peers. Ultimately, the concept of fair value provides investors, stakeholders, and market participants with an objective framework for evaluating the worth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, enabling informed investment decisions and promoting market efficiency and transparency.

2.1.8 Price-to-book value

Price-to-book value (P/B ratio) is a financial metric used by investors and analysts to evaluate the valuation of a company relative to its balance sheet assets. The P/B ratio compares a company's market price per share to its book value per share, which is derived from the company's total assets minus its total liabilities, divided by the number of outstanding shares. The market price per share represents the current market value of a company's stock as determined by supply and demand in the open market. It is the price at which shares are bought and sold on stock exchanges (Duho, 2021).

The book value per share, on the other hand, represents the theoretical value of a company's equity if all its assets were liquidated and all its debts were paid off. It is calculated by dividing the company's total equity (assets minus liabilities) by the number of outstanding shares. A P/B ratio of 1 indicates that the market price of the stock is equal to its book value. A P/B ratio below 1 suggests that the stock is trading at a discount to its book value, which may indicate that the stock is undervalued. Conversely, a P/B ratio above 1 implies that the stock is trading at a premium to its book value, which may suggest that the stock is overvalued.

2.1.9 Human capital and price-to-book value

The relationship between human capital and the price-to-book value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria is a complex and multifaceted one that involves various dynamics related to talent management, organizational performance, market perceptions, and investor valuation. Human capital, which refers to the skills, knowledge, experience, and capabilities of employees within an organization, plays a critical role in driving innovation, productivity, and competitiveness in the industrial sector. Investors and

financial analysts often use the price-to-book value ratio as a key indicator of a company's valuation relative to its tangible assets and equity value. A high price-to-book value ratio suggests that investors are willing to pay a premium for the company's stock, indicating positive market sentiment and expectations for future growth and profitability. On the other hand, a low price-to-book value ratio may signal undervaluation or perceived risks associated with the company's financial health, growth prospects, or competitive position. In the context of industrial goods firms in Nigeria, the relationship between human capital and price-to-book value can be analyzed from multiple perspectives as opined by Anifowose et al., (2017).

Talent and Innovation; Human capital, including skilled workforce, technical expertise, and innovative capabilities, can drive product development, process improvements, and technological advancements that enhance the firm's competitive advantage and market presence. Companies with a highly skilled and motivated workforce are better positioned to generate superior returns on investments, attract strategic partnerships, and create sustainable value for shareholders, leading to a higher price-to-book value ratio as reported by Idigo, (2023).

Secondly, operational Performance; the quality of human capital, such as strong leadership, effective management, employee engagement, and talent retention, has a direct impact on operational efficiency, cost management, and revenue generation within industrial firms. Well-managed companies that invest in employee training, development, and performance incentives are likely to achieve higher profitability, cash flow generation, and asset utilization, which can influence their price-to-book value positively as seen in Xu and Liu, (2020).

Thirdly, reputation and Investor Confidence; the reputation of a company as an employer of choice, a responsible corporate citizen, and a leader in industry best practices can enhance its brand equity, stakeholder relationships, and long-term sustainability. Firms that prioritize human capital development, diversity and inclusion, employee well-being, and ethical business conduct are more likely to gain the trust and confidence of investors, analysts, and regulatory bodies, potentially resulting in a premium valuation reflected in a higher price-to-book value ratio (Ullah et al., 2021). Lastly industry Dynamics and Market Sentiment; external factors, such as macroeconomic conditions, regulatory environment, industry trends, competitive landscape, and investor sentiment, can also influence the relationship between human capital and price-to-book value for industrial goods firms in Nigeria (Reason & Imo, 2023). Companies that navigate market uncertainties, adapt to technological disruptions, seize growth opportunities, and demonstrate resilience in challenging times may command a higher market valuation based on their ability to leverage human capital as a strategic asset for sustainable performance and value creation as recorded by Idigo, (2023) alongside Chukwu and Nwachukwu, (2021).

2.1.11 Structural capital and price-to-book value

The relationship between structural capital and price-to-book (P/B) value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria is a complex and multifaceted one. Structural capital, which encompasses the organizational and technological infrastructure of a firm, plays a crucial role in driving the financial performance and market valuation of Industrial goods firms. In Nigeria, listed Industrial goods firms with strong structural capital are likely to have a higher P/B value. This is because structural capital enables firms to improve their operational efficiency, reduce costs, and increase their competitiveness in the market. For instance, firms with well-developed information technology systems and efficient supply chain management are better positioned to respond to changes in the market and to capitalize on new opportunities (Nawaz & Haniffa, 2017). Make-up designs enhance cultural aesthetics, artistic style and tradition as cited by Umoh, (2018).

Structural capital can also enhance the innovation capabilities of Industrial goods firms, enabling them to develop new products and services that meet the evolving needs of their customers. This, in turn, can lead to increased revenue and profitability, which can drive up the P/B value of the firm (Idigo, 2023). Entrepreneurship is a first-class global theory through which many first world nations expand their economic strength as opined by Umoh, (2021). Furthermore, the quality of structural capital can also influence the risk perception of investors, with firms having strong structural capital being perceived as

less risky. This can lead to a higher P/B value, as investors are willing to pay a premium for firms with strong structural capital (Nawaz & Haniffa, 2017). The primary fiscal balance is a non-debt deficit (Ekaetor et al. 2024)

Akpan and Akininyi (2019) opined that the Nigerian stock market, like many emerging markets, is characterized by a high level of information asymmetry. In such an environment, structural capital can serve as a signal of a firm's quality and prospects, enabling investors to make more informed decisions. Firms with strong structural capital are likely to be perceived as more transparent and accountable, which can lead to a higher P/B value. However, it is also important to note that the relationship between structural capital and P/B value can be influenced by various factors, including the industry and market conditions, the quality of corporate governance, and the level of investor sentiment. Moreover, the measurement of structural capital can be challenging, and different proxies may be used to capture its different dimensions. The relationship between structural capital and P/B value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria is complex and multifaceted. Firms with strong structural capital are likely to have a higher P/B value, driven by their improved operational efficiency, innovation capabilities, and risk profile. The bigger companies are more likely to have more resources, more visibility, and more scrutiny of their practices and disclosure (John et al. 2025).

2.1.12 Relational capital and price-to-book value

Relational capital, a component of intellectual capital, refers to the value derived from relationships, networks, and interactions that a company has with its stakeholders, including customers, suppliers, partners, employees, investors, and communities. In the context of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, relational capital plays a significant role in shaping the firm's reputation, brand equity, market positioning, and long-term competitiveness. The relationship between relational capital and the price-to-book value of industrial goods firms can be analyzed through various lenses to understand the impact of intangible assets on financial performance and investor valuation (Idigo, 2023). Effective management of relational capital involves building and nurturing strong connections with key stakeholders to create mutual trust, collaboration, and value creation. Companies that prioritize customer relationships, supplier partnerships, employee engagement, investor communication, and community outreach can develop a reservoir of goodwill, credibility, and loyalty that enhances their competitive advantage and market perception as reported by Xu and Liu, (2020). By leveraging relational capital as a strategic asset, industrial goods firms in Nigeria can drive business growth, innovation, and sustainable development while influencing their financial metrics, including the price-to-book value ratio (Susshua & Karam, 2012).

Chiucchi et al., (2018) recorded that Industrial goods firms that focus on understanding customer needs, delivering quality products, and providing excellent service are likely to build strong customer relationships based on trust, satisfaction, and loyalty. Positive customer experiences, repeat business, and referrals can contribute to revenue growth, market share expansion, and brand differentiation, which may be reflected in a higher price-to-book value ratio as investors recognize the value of loyal customer base and market reputation. Collaborative relationships with suppliers, vendors, and partners are essential for ensuring a reliable supply chain, cost efficiency, and product quality within the industrial sector. Companies that maintain transparent, fair, and strategic supplier relationships can improve operational performance, mitigate risks, and enhance their competitive position in the market, potentially leading to a higher price-to-book value ratio as investors perceive strong supply chain management practices and strategic sourcing capabilities (Anifowose et al., 2017). The attempt to capture nature in its most proximal form may appear illusive especially when art and life differ in substance and form based approach as stated by Umoh & Atakpo, (2025)

According to Idigo, (2023) engaged and motivated employees play a crucial role in driving productivity, innovation, and organizational performance in industrial goods firms. Companies that invest in employee development, empowerment, recognition, and well-being can cultivate a positive work culture, high levels of job satisfaction, and talent retention, thereby improving operational efficiency, employee productivity, and overall business outcomes. A committed and skilled workforce can contribute to higher profitability, growth potential, and shareholder value, which may be reflected in a premium valuation indicated by a

higher price-to-book value ratio. Transparent communication, financial reporting, and stakeholder engagement are key elements of effective investor relations for industrial goods firms seeking to attract and retain investors in the capital markets (Nassar, 2018).

2.1.13 Innovation capital and price-to-book value

The relationship between innovation capital and price-to-book (P/B) value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria is a significant one. Innovation capital, which encompasses a firm's innovation capabilities, research and development (R&D) activities, and intellectual property, can have a positive impact on a firm's financial performance and market valuation (Araniyar & Chizea, 2017). Employee's personality refers to a combination of behavioral,

Physical and mental characteristics that are unique for the individuals as cited by (Etim, Brownson & Akpaetor, 2023). In the context of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria, innovation capital can drive growth, improve competitiveness, and enhance profitability. Firms with strong innovation capital are likely to develop new products, services, and processes that meet the evolving needs of their customers, which can lead to increased revenue and market share (Adesanmi, 2021). As a result, investors are likely to place a higher value on firms with strong innovation capital, as they are perceived to have a higher potential for growth and returns. The introduction of new products or techniques or of a new that consumers are not yet familiar with as cited by (Umoh, 2024). This can lead to a higher P/B value, as investors are willing to pay a premium for firms with strong innovation capital (Akpan and Akinniyi, 2019). Market risks encompass the challenges related to the external environment in which a start-up operates (Edet et al. 2024).

In Nigeria, the relationship between innovation capital and P/B value may be influenced by various factors, including the industry and market conditions, the quality of corporate governance, and the level of investor sentiment (Andreeva & Garanina, 2017). However, in general, firms with strong innovation capital are likely to have a higher P/B value, as investors place a premium on firms with high growth potential and competitiveness (Buallay, 2017).

2.1.14 Process capital and price-to-book value

Akpan and Akinniyi (2019) documented that intellectual capital plays a vital role in driving the performance and value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, with process capital being a key component that influences the price-to-book value ratio. Process capital refers to the knowledge, systems, and procedures embedded within an organization that contribute to its operational efficiency and effectiveness as seen in Eka et al., (2019). In the context of industrial goods firms, efficient processes are crucial for enhancing productivity, reducing costs, and improving overall performance. Companies that effectively manage and optimize their process capital are likely to achieve higher levels of operational excellence, which can positively impact their price-to-book value ratio. Chirkova et al., (2018) posited that streamlining operations, automating workflows, and continuously improving processes, industrial goods firms can enhance their competitiveness, profitability, and market valuation.

The relationship between process capital and the price-to-book value ratio of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria is influenced by several factors. Firstly, efficient processes enable companies to deliver products and services more effectively, resulting in higher customer satisfaction, increased market share, and stronger brand reputation (Adesanmi, 2021). These intangible assets, driven by effective process capital management, can have a direct impact on the market perception of the firm's value and contribute to a higher price-to-book value ratio. Additionally, by investing in process innovation, technology adoption, and employee training, industrial goods firms can enhance their capabilities, drive growth, and generate sustainable competitive advantages that are reflected in their market valuation. Companies that leverage their process capital to drive continuous improvement and operational excellence are better positioned to attract investors, unlock shareholder value, and achieve a higher price-to-book value ratio in the long term as reported by Adesanmi, (2021). Creativity denotes bringing new ideas to reality through imagination. It suggests innovativeness through thought (Umoh & Ekpo, 2025).

2.2 Theoretical framework

2.2.1 Resource-based view (RBV) theory by Edith Penrose (1959)

The Resource-based view (RBV) theory, proposed by Edith Penrose in 1959, examines how a firm's unique resources and capabilities can lead to competitive advantage, superior financial performance and value. This theory sees intellectual capital as unique and valuable resource of a firm. In the context of intellectual capital and the fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Intellectual capital refers to intangible assets possessed by a firm, including knowledge, expertise, patents, trademarks, and copyrights (Andreeva & Garanina, 2017). These assets can contribute significantly to a firm's competitive advantage which will definitely reflect in its fair value. In the case of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, their intellectual capital may include innovative technologies, research and development capabilities, organizational know-how, brand reputation, and customer relationships. Enhanced intellectual capital can lead to improved product differentiation, operational efficiency, and customer loyalty as suggested by Alipour, (2012). These factors can result in increased market share, revenue growth, and profitability, ultimately contributing to a higher fair value for the firm.

In addition, the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory emphasizes that sustained competitive advantage is achieved when a firm possesses unique and difficult-to-imitate resources. Intellectual capital, being intangible and complex to replicate, can provide a source of competitive advantage for listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. This can further enhance their fair value. RBV suggests that the effectiveness of intellectual capital in enhancing fair value depends on how well it is integrated within the firm's overall resource portfolio and strategic capabilities. Listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria need to align their intellectual capital with other tangible and intangible resources, such as physical assets, operational efficiencies, supply chain management, and customer service, to maximize their impact on fair value. The synergy created by integrating intellectual capital with other resources can lead to sustainable competitive advantage and higher fair value (Nuryaman, 2015). In conclusion, the Resource-Based View theory explains that intellectual capital can be a valuable resource that contributes to the fair value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. By leveraging their intellectual capital effectively, these firms can gain a competitive advantage, enhance their market position, and achieve higher fair value in the marketplace. The Resource-based view (RBV) theory will be the most appropriate for this study because through leveraging their intellectual capital effectively, industrial goods firms can gain a competitive advantage over other sector, enhance their market position, and also achieve higher fair value in the market place.

2.2.2 The Signalling theory by Michael Spence, (1973).

The signaling theory, developed by Michael Spence in 1973, provides a framework for understanding how intellectual capital can influence the fair value of listed Consumer goods firms in Nigeria. According to the signaling theory, firms can convey information about their intellectual capital to investors through various signals, such as research and development (R&D) investments, patent filings, employee expertise, and innovation capabilities. In the context of listed Consumer goods firms in Nigeria, intellectual capital can serve as a signal of a firm's ability to innovate, adapt to changing market conditions, and create value for shareholders. Firms with high levels of intellectual capital, such as those with strong R&D capabilities, innovative products, and skilled employees, are likely to send strong signals to investors about their growth potential and competitiveness (Aluwong, 2022). These signals can influence investors' perceptions of the firm's value and, subsequently, its fair value. Investors who perceive a firm's intellectual capital as strong are likely to place a higher value on the firm, leading to a higher fair value. On the other hand, firms with weak intellectual capital are likely to send weak signals to investors, leading to a lower fair value (Alipour 2012).

The signaling theory also suggests that the quality and credibility of the signals sent by firms can influence their impact on fair value. For example, firms that consistently invest in R&D and innovation are likely to send stronger signals to investors than firms that only occasionally invest in these areas. The theory can be particularly relevant due to the high level of information asymmetry in the market. Investors may rely heavily on signals sent by firms to make informed decisions about their investments. Therefore, firms with strong intellectual capital can benefit from sending strong signals to investors,

which can lead to a higher fair value. The signaling theory provides a useful framework for understanding the relationship between intellectual capital and fair value of listed Consumer goods firms in Nigeria. By sending strong signals about their intellectual capital, firms can influence investors' perceptions of their value and, subsequently, their fair value.

2.3 Empirical framework

Romano et al., (2025) assessed intellectual capital-based research impact management: A strategic approach to increase regional intellectual capital. Entrepreneurial universities, through their intellectual capital (IC), can promote the development of a third mission, which involves collaborating with business and societal organizations to create value. Joint research projects are undertaken within entrepreneurial universities leveraging their IC. These generate value for both the academic community and the territory as they generate impact, in terms of regional IC. At the micro level, scientists in the principal investigator (PI) role are influential actors in generating impact and IC that is beneficial for all joint project stakeholders. The purpose of the paper is to address the existing gap in entrepreneurial university literature concerning the impact generation process. The paper represents a theoretical contribution adopting a deductive approach. This paper proposes a novel approach to support PIs in entrepreneurial universities in the process of managing innovative initiatives toward IC impact generation. First, we present the IC-based Research Impact Tool (ICRIT) to guide PIs acting as explorative entrepreneurs; then we propose an IC-based Research Impact Report (ICRIR) including some key performance indicators (KPIs) to evaluate impact and IC.

Rong et al., (2025) examined the impact of intellectual capital on the overall value of commercial banks within the European Union (EU). The research aims to identify how these banks can evaluate and enhance their intellectual capital to improve operational performance. The study employs the value-added intellectual coefficient (VAIC) model to measure the efficiency of three types of capital: structural capital (SC), which is the value added by the company minus human capital; employed physical and financial capital (CE), representing the total financial capital available to the company; and human capital (HC), calculated based on employee costs. Data were sourced from the BankScope database, comprising published financial reports of 599 commercial banks. Control variables included loan quality, fund utilization ratio, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The research identifies a significant positive correlation between financial capital, human capital, and the value-added function of banks. These findings suggest that financial and human capital are critical determinants of value addition in commercial banks within the EU. This study uniquely focuses on the intellectual capital performance of EU-based banks. To the best of our knowledge, such a comprehensive analysis on this subject within the context of EU banks has not been previously conducted.

Jordão et al., (2025) aimed to analyze the impact of intellectual capital (IC) on Brazilian companies' sustainable value creation (VC). An empirical study was performed using descriptive and multivariate statistics based on the finance, strategy and IC theories. This research is quantitative, explanatory, descriptive, applied and ex post facto and uses traditional economic-financial variables (derived from financial statements – FSS) linked to two established frameworks for IC analysis: the market-to-book ratio (IC-INDEX) and the MVAIC, a variation of the value-added intellectual coefficient (VAIC™). The findings showed that the IC estimated through the IC-INDEX and the MVAIC frameworks is directly related to the VC of Brazilian companies throughout the entire period and revealed a consistent effect in all time frames analyzed. Both models were robust and complementary in assessing the company's VC and sustainability. The conclusion shows that IC is the most relevant factor in explaining VC and its continuity over time, regardless of other traditional variables used to study the phenomenon.

Ramos-Rodriguez et al., (2024) researched on what you know or who you know? The role of intellectual and social capital in opportunity recognition. The recognition of business opportunities is the first stage in the entrepreneurial process. The current work analyzes the effects of individuals' possession of and access to knowledge on the probability of recognizing good business opportunities in their area of residence. The authors use an eclectic theoretical framework consisting of intellectual and social capital concepts. In particular, they analyze the role of individuals' educational level, their perception that they have the right

knowledge and skills to start a business, whether they own and manage a firm, their contacts with other entrepreneurs, and whether they have been business angels. The hypotheses proposed here are tested using data collected for the GEM project in Spain in 2007. The results show that individuals' access to external knowledge through the social networks in which they participate is fundamental for developing the capacity to recognize new business opportunities.

Mohammed (2024) analyzed performance measurement in the government sector: Between reality and aspiration. The current study was performed to analyze various factors having an impact on the performance measurement of the government sector. Data was collected quantitatively and qualitatively to evaluate the study. The questionnaire and the secondary data were used to analyze the factors having an influence on the performance measurement while detailed questions were asked to address the whys to minimize the gap between aspiration and reality. In the quantitative study, data interpretation was done by using SPSS software. Regression statistics were applied to identify the relation between both variables i.e., dependent and independent. While, for qualitative search strategy thematic analysis was done. The results of the study suggest a positive relation of the factors with the performance measurement. In the end, the study concluded that by implementing a performance measuring strategy in the government sector, accurate and efficient performance would be gained.

Idigo, (2023) investigated the effect of intellectual capital on organizational productivity in selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. The study was anchored on Human Capital Theory and adopted descriptive research survey design. The population of the study was one thousand two hundred (1200). The statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall (1973) was employed to determine the sample size of two hundred and four (300). Multiple regression analysis were employed to analyze the data generated. The study concluded that intellectual capital had a strong positive significant effect on organizational productivity in manufacturing firms in South-East Nigeria.

Habib and Dalwa (2023), explores on the efficiency of intellectual capital (ICE) and working capital management (WCME) in the GCC industrial sector and its potential impact on firm performance. The data were gathered from Standard & Poor's database from 2015 to 2019. This study uses data envelopment analysis (DEA), regression analysis, and robustness tests to accomplish its aims. The results indicate that most firms do not employ their intellectual and working capital investments well and need improvement actions to achieve the best practices. The regression model results reveal that ICE and WCME significantly and positively influence firms' performance. The results of this study support the resource-based, trade-off, and pecking order theories. The study findings have important implications for many stakeholders; for example, they would be helpful for firm decision-makers in managing their investments in intellectual and working capital to achieve the best practices and improve a firm's performance. In addition, the findings would be helpful for financiers, because high-performance firms are likely to have more reasonable valuations that facilitate debt financing. Moreover, the findings have noteworthy implications for trading procedures as investors aspire to attractive economic returns for their investments in corporations that pasture ICE and WCME issues. Additionally, these findings have important implications for employee job satisfaction and retention by improving IC management.

Reason and Imo, (2023) investigated on intellectual capital and financial performance using a causal study design. The study adopted ex-post facto research design on a population of twenty-six (26) insurance companies listed on the Nigeria stock exchange. The census method was adopted to opt for all of twenty-six (26) insurance companies. However, only thirteen (13) of the companies had complete data for the period under review (2012 to 2020). Therefore, the sample size of the study was thirteen (13). Given the period of nine (9) years (2012-2020), the study used 117 firm year observations. The statistical model adopted in this study were; descriptive statistics and multiple regression technique for the analysis data with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The study found that, Human Capital Efficiency, Structural Capital Efficiency and Capital Employed Efficiency have minimal significant and positive effect on Return on Asset. The study concludes that all the indicators of intellectual capital show that there is no much significant effect on financial performance of insurance companies in Nigeria, and recommends amongst others that, the International Financial Reporting Committee (IFRC) to develop

standard that will make intellectual capital reporting compulsory in the financial statement in order to enhance financial reporting quality and performance within the context of satisfying the information need of stakeholders

METHODOLOGY

This work adopted an *ex-post facto* research design. This design was suitable because the data for the analysis had already transpired, leaving little or no room for the researcher to manipulate it. In this study, the population was made up of all industrial goods firms listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group from 2015 to 2024. As of December 31st, 2024, the total number of industrial goods firms in Nigeria was thirteen (13). A sample size of nine (9) listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria was arrived purposively after subjecting it to a validity test using Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) formula. The Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) formula is given as follows;

$$n \geq 50 + 8(m)$$

Where; n = number of pooled observation

m = number of predictor variables, i.e 5.

50+8(m) = minimum number of pooled observation.

Therefore, $n \geq 50 + 8(5)$

$$81 > 82$$

In line with the above, considering four (5) predictor variables for this study, the minimum number of pooled observations for this study was 90 while the number of pooled observations with a sample size of nine (9) is 81. (i.e 9 by 9). Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the required sample. However, availability of data served as the yardstick for selection (Emenyi, 2024¹). The technique enhances the selection of industrial goods firms that were continuously listed by Nigerian exchange group during the period (2015-2024) and whose financial statements and reports are available and have been consistently submitted to Nigeria exchange group for the period under study. The data for the dependent and independent variables was extracted from financial reports using contents analysis method and collated with the aid of Microsoft excel software. The panel data methodology was adopted because the study combined time series and cross-sectional data. The study adopted panel least squares regression to analyze data via E-views 10.0. The data conformed to the standardized regression assumptions, that is, linearity, homoscedasticity, normality and independence of data. Durbin Watson statistics is within the range of 2-4. The decision was based on 5% level of significance. Accept null hypothesis (Ho) if probability value (i.e. P-value or Sig.) is greater than or equals to (\geq) stated 5% level of significance (α); otherwise, reject and accept alternate hypothesis (H₁), if p-value or sig calculated is less than 5% level of significance

To achieve the stated objectives of the study, as well as testing the study hypotheses, a multiple linear regression model was adopted as follows;

$$P/B_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 HCAP_{it} + \beta_2 SCAP_{it} + \beta_3 RCAP + \beta_4 INCAP_{it} + \beta_5 PCAP_{it} + e_{it}$$

Where;

Y_{it} = Dependent variable;

α_i = Intercept or regression constant;

e_{it} = Error term.

P/B = Price-to-book value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

HCAP = Human capital of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

SCAP= Structural capital of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

RCAP = Relational capital of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

INCAP = Innovation capital of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

PCAP = Process capital of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

x_i = Independent variable

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Regression coefficient

Table 3.1 below depicts the measurement of the variables defined in the model above.

Table 3.1 Measurement of variables

Concept	Proxy	Measurement	Source
Intellectual capital (Independent variable)	Human capital	Revenue minus operating expenses divided by the number of employees.	Onyekweluea <i>et al.</i> , (2017).
	Structural capital	Total of shareholder's fund / total asset	Iwan & Azhar (2016)
	Relational capital	Net promoters score via industry rating.	Aluwong, (2022) Nassar, (2018).
	Innovation capital	R&D expenses / revenue	Adesanmi, (2021)
	Process capital	Measured using inventory turnover (In days).	Onyekweluea <i>et al.</i> , (2017).
Fair value (Dependent variable)	Price-to-book value	Ratio of market value to book value per share.	Handam, (2018)

Source: Author's conceptualization (2025).

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section focuses on the presentation of data, analysis of the data, testing of the research hypotheses as well as the discussion of findings based on the results obtained.

4.1 Data presentation

The data for this study is presented in table 4.1 (see Appendix I). The data comprise a panel data of ninety (90) pooled observations gathered across nine (9) listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria over a period of ten (10) years (2015-2024). The data include the independent variable (intellectual capital) which was proxied by human capital, structural capital, relational capital, innovation capital and process capital as well as the dependent variable (fair value) proxied by price-to-book value) of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

4.2 Data analysis

Various statistical techniques were utilized in the analysis of data presented in table 4.1 (see Appendix 2). These include descriptive statistics, regression assumption tests and panel multiple regression analysis. The results from the panel multiple regression analysis were used in the testing of the research hypotheses which had been stated in the first chapter of this work.

4.2.1 Descriptive statistics

This was conducted to understand the behaviour of the data using various statistics including mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. The result for the descriptive statistics analysis is as presented in Table 4.2 below;

Table 4.2 Descriptive statistics results

	P_B	HCAP	SCAP	RCAP	INCAP	PCAP
Mean	2.296478	42685.79	0.426388	15.73195	0.075647	82.99471
Median	1.885000	7395.025	0.466769	15.58464	0.016014	83.74500
Maximum	8.080000	382871.2	0.747163	19.74207	0.883543	111.9900
Minimum	0.000000	70.15965	0.004183	12.85625	5.98E-05	56.45000
Std. Dev.	1.854553	91450.09	0.226083	1.847030	0.159496	11.26865
Skewness	0.836825	2.577716	-0.762007	0.584073	3.074381	0.140726
Kurtosis	3.305211	8.260629	2.377448	2.515002	12.52181	2.663083
Jarque-Bera	10.85347	203.4476	10.16321	5.999208	481.7706	0.722732
Probability	0.004397	0.000000	0.006210	0.049807	0.000000	0.696724
Sum	206.6830	3841722.	38.37488	1415.876	6.808232	7469.524
Sum Sq. Dev.	306.1038	7.44E+11	4.549106	303.6253	2.264080	11301.45
Observations	90	90	90	90	90	90

Source: Researcher's computation using E-views 10.0 (2025)

The results in table 4.2 above indicates that the dependent variable- price-to-book value and the independent variables which were human capital, structural capital, relational capital, innovation capital and process capital of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria have mean scores of approximately 2.296, 42685, 0.426, 15.732, 0.0756 and 82.995 respectively. This indicates the central or average values for these variables from 2014 to 2023. The median values obtained for price-to-book value, human capital, structural capital, relational capital, innovation capital and process capital of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria were approximately 1.885, 7395, 0.4667, 15.585, 0.016 and 83.745 respectively. These constitute the middle values for the distributions of these variables under the period covered in this study (2015-2024).

In terms of the level of variability and dispersion in the distribution of these variables, the standard deviations obtained for price-to-book value, human capital, structural capital, relational capital, innovation capital and process capital of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria were approximately 1.854, 91450, 0.2260, 1.847, 0.159 and 11.268 respectively. This indicates varying levels of variability in the distribution with human capital indicating high variations in the distributions. Similarly, the skewness values obtained for price-to-book value, human capital, structural capital, relational capital, innovation capital and process capital of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria were 0.836, 2.577, -0.762, 0.584, 3.0743 and 0.1407 respectively. This quantifies the asymmetry of the distributions.

In addition, the Kurtosis values obtained for price-to-book value, human capital, structural capital, relational capital, innovation capital and process capital of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria were given as approximately 3.3052, 8.2606, 2.377, 2.515, 12.521 and 2.663 respectively. Since the values of the kurtosis are greater than zero (0), it indicates a leptokurtic distribution, hence the presence of outliers in the data.

4.2.2 Model evaluation

Residual and coefficient diagnostics were however conducted to assess the suitability of the model as stated in the previous section. These include normality test, multicollinearity test, heteroscedasticity test and autocorrelation assessment.

4.2.2.1 Normality test

Fig. 4.1 Jarque-Bera Normality test results

Source: E-views 10.0 Output (2025)

The essence of a normality test is to determine if a dataset or sample follows a normal distribution. This is important because many statistical models assume normality, and deviations from normality can affect the validity of statistical inference. The Jarque-Bera test was employed in this case. As applied, if the p-value associated with the Jarque-Bera test is below a predetermined significance level ($p < 0.05$), then we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the data do not follow a normal distribution. With a p-value of 0.896227, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the data were normally distributed.

4.2.2.2 Multicollinearity test

In examining the association among the variables, the study employed the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient (correlation matrix), and the results are presented in the table below.

Table 4.3 Spearman’s rank correlation matrix

	P_B	HCAP	SCAP	RCAP	INCAP	PCAP
P_B	1.000000	-0.223757	0.435944	-0.176492	0.085084	0.076968
HCAP	-0.223757	1.000000	-0.113619	0.189711	-0.140919	-0.218630
SCAP	0.435944	-0.113619	1.000000	-0.096168	-0.117257	0.317312
RCAP	-0.176492	0.189711	-0.096168	1.000000	-0.211680	-0.222903
INCAP	0.085084	-0.140919	-0.117257	-0.211680	1.000000	0.080355
PCAP	0.076968	-0.218630	0.317312	-0.222903	0.080355	1.000000

Source: E-views 10.0 Output (2025)

The correlation analysis showed that all independent variables by human capital, structural capital, relational capital, innovation capital and process capital have coefficients lesser than 0.80 respectively confirming absence of multicollinearity issues.

4.2.2.3 Heteroscedasticity test

Table 4.4 Heteroscedasticity test

Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Breusch-Pagan LM	262.3880	153	0.0610
Pesaran scaled LM	15.24302		0.0451
Pesaran CD	-1.094252		0.2738

Source: E-views 10.0 (2025)

Heteroscedasticity refers to the unequal spread of residuals (or errors) across the range of predictor variables in a regression model. Heteroscedasticity tests aim to detect this violation of the assumption of constant variance. Common tests include the Breusch-Pagan test and the White test, which assess the relationship between the squared residuals and the predictor variables. The statistics and probability value associated with the Breusch-Pagan LM test otherwise known as the Breusch-Pagan Godfrey test help determine whether there is evidence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model. A low p-value ($p < 0.05$) suggests evidence against the null hypothesis in favour of the alternate hypothesis which indicates the presence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model. With a p-value of 0.0610, there is sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis, thus, conclude that the predictor variables in the regression model were homoscedastic.

4.2.2.4 Autocorrelation

Autocorrelation, also known as serial correlation, occurs when there is a correlation between the residual errors of a time series or panel data over time. Autocorrelation tests examine whether the residuals are independently distributed or if there is a systematic pattern of dependence. The Durbin-Watson statistic is commonly used to test for autocorrelation, with values close to 2 indicating no significant autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic as obtained from the panel regression results (see Appendix II) was utilized in this case. The Durbin-Watson statistic value of 1.735231 suggests a mild positive autocorrelation present in the residuals of the regression model.

4.3 Test of hypotheses

Each of the hypotheses in this study was tested based on the result obtained from the panel multiple regression analysis. The result that relates to these hypotheses is summarized in table 4.5 below;

Table 4.5 Panel multiple regression results

Dependent Variable: P_B
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 07/17/25 Time: 21:01
 Sample: 2015 2024
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 9
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 90

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-5.164803	2.929606	-1.762968	0.0815
HCAP	1.280405	3.09E-06	4.146622	0.0001
SCAP	4.128763	0.785100	5.258899	0.0000
RCAP	0.529721	0.169708	3.121374	0.0025
INCAP	2.259483	1.216742	1.856995	0.0668
PCAP	-0.027189	0.015818	-1.718817	0.0893
R-squared	0.648508	Mean dependent var		2.296478
Adjusted R-squared	0.609729	S.D. dependent var		1.854553
S.E. of regression	1.540810	Akaike info criterion		3.766834
Sum squared resid	199.4240	Schwarz criterion		3.933488
Log likelihood	-163.5075	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.834039
F-statistic	8.986979	Durbin-Watson stat		1.735231
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001			

Source: Researcher’s computation using E-views 10.0 (2025)

The multiple regression line is as written below:

$$P_B = -5.16480335777 + 1.28173955595e-05*HCAP + 4.12876326803*SCAP + 0.529721029894*RCAP + 2.25948338914*INCAP - 0.0271887176436*PCAP + \mu$$

The regression analysis reveals that human capital (HCAP), structural capital (SCAP), relational capital (RCAP), and innovation capital (INCAP) have positive relationships with fair value, suggesting that investments in these areas can enhance firm value. Specifically, a unit increase in SCAP, RCAP, and INCAP is associated with increases of 1.28, 4.13, 0.53, and 2.26 units in price-to-book value, respectively. Conversely, process capital (PCAP) exhibit negative relationships, implying potential inefficiencies or over-investment in these areas.

The R-squared (0.65) and Adjusted R-squared (0.61) values indicate that approximately 65% of the variation in fair value is explained by the intellectual capital components. The Adjusted R-squared, which penalizes for model complexity, remains relatively high at 0.61, suggesting that the model has reasonable explanatory power.

4.3.1 Hypothesis one

H₀: There is no significant relationship between human capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

H₁: There is significant relationship between human capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

In order to test whether the variations in price-to-earnings ratio of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria caused by human capital is significant. The T-test was carried out at .05 significance level with Ttab of 2.26215 given at τ_{0.05,9}. From the result above, the Tcal of 4.1466 is greater than Ttab given at τ_{0.05,9}. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between human capital and price-to-book value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria fails to hold, thus rejected, and

the alternative hypothesis accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that at $T_{0.05,19}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.0001) is less than 0.05.

4.3.2 Hypothesis two

H₀: There is no significant relationship between structural capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria

H₁: There is significant relationship between structural capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria

Given T_{tab} of 2.109 at $T_{0.05,9}$, the T_{cal} of 5.258899 is greater than T_{tab}. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that the probability value (p-value = 0.0000) is less than 0.05.

4.3.3 Hypothesis three

H₀: There is no significant relationship between relational capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

H₁: There is significant relationship between relational capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Given T_{tab} of 2.109 at $T_{0.05,9}$, the T_{cal} of 3.121374 is greater than T_{tab}. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that the probability value (p-value = 0.0025) is less than 0.05.

4.3.4 Hypothesis four

H₀: There is no significant relationship between innovation capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria

H₁: There is significant relationship between innovation capital and price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria

Given T_{tab} of 2.109 at $T_{0.05,9}$, the T_{cal} of 1.856995 is less than T_{tab}. Hence, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The null hypothesis is further not rejected given that the probability value (p-value = 0.0668) is greater than 0.05.

4.3.5 Hypothesis five

H₀: Process capital has no significant relationship with price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria

H₁: Process capital has significant relationship with price-to-book value of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria

Given T_{tab} of 2.26215 at $T_{0.05,9}$, the absolute value of T_{cal} of -1.718817, is less than T_{tab}. Hence, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The null hypothesis is further not rejected given that the probability value (p-value = 0.0893) is greater than 0.05.

4.4 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.4.1 Human capital and price-to-book value

The significant positive relationship between human capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 1.280405, p-value = 0.0001) suggests that investments in human capital are crucial for enhancing firm value in listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Human capital, which encompasses the knowledge, skills, and expertise of employees, is a vital component of intellectual capital. The finding implies that firms that invest in human capital development, such as training and development programs, talent acquisition and retention, and employee empowerment, are likely to experience an increase in their market value.

This is consistent with the resource-based view of the firm, which posits that firms with unique and valuable resources, such as human capital, can achieve sustainable competitive advantage and superior performance. The finding highlights the importance of human capital in driving firm value and suggests that industrial goods firms in Nigeria should prioritize investments in human capital development to enhance their competitiveness and market value. The significant positive relationship between human capital and price-to-book value is consistent with previous studies. For instance, Idigo (2023) found that intellectual capital had a strong positive significant effect on organizational productivity in manufacturing

firms in South-East Nigeria, while Izuchukwu (2023) reported that human capital had a positive and significant effect on profitability of health care firms in Nigeria. Similarly, Ogbaro et al. (2022) found that human capital development contributed positively to the performance of commercial banks in Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. These studies highlight the importance of human capital in driving firm performance and value.

4.4.2 Structural capital and price-to-book value

The significant positive relationship between structural capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 4.128763, p-value = 0.0000) indicates that effective organizational structures and systems are essential for enhancing firm value in listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Structural capital, which includes organizational culture, processes, and systems, provides the framework for firms to operate efficiently and effectively. The finding suggests that firms with well-designed organizational structures and systems are likely to experience an increase in their market value. This is consistent with the knowledge-based view of the firm, which emphasizes the importance of organizational knowledge and capabilities in driving firm performance. The finding highlights the critical role of structural capital in driving firm value and suggests that industrial goods firms in Nigeria should prioritize investments in organizational design, process improvement, and system development to enhance their competitiveness and market value.

The significant positive relationship between structural capital and price-to-book value is also consistent with previous studies. Aluwong (2022) found that structural capital efficiency significantly improves firm performance proxied by return on assets, while Chukwu and Nwachukwu (2021) reported that structural capital efficiency has a positive and significant relationship with firm performance in selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Kasoga (2020) also found that structural capital efficiency has a significant positive influence on firm performance in Tanzania. These studies demonstrate the critical role of structural capital in driving firm performance and value.

4.4.3 Relational capital and price-to-book value

The significant positive relationship between relational capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 0.529721, p-value = 0.0025) suggests that strong relationships with stakeholders, such as customers and suppliers, are vital for enhancing firm value in listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Relational capital, which encompasses the relationships and networks that firms have with their stakeholders, is a critical component of intellectual capital. The finding implies that firms that invest in building and maintaining strong relationships with their stakeholders are likely to experience an increase in their market value. This is consistent with the stakeholder theory, which posits that firms that prioritize the interests of their stakeholders are likely to achieve superior performance and sustainability. The finding highlights the importance of relational capital in driving firm value and suggests that industrial goods firms in Nigeria should prioritize investments in relationship-building and stakeholder engagement to enhance their competitiveness and market value.

The significant positive relationship between relational capital and price-to-book value is consistent with previous studies. Muftiasa et al. (2023) found that relational capital has a statistically significant and positively impacting relationship with firm performance in the telecommunications sector during the post-COVID-19 era. Aljuboori et al. (2022) also reported that relational capital has a positive effect on firm performance in Malaysian SMEs. These studies highlight the importance of relational capital in driving firm performance and value.

4.4.4 Innovation capital and price-to-book value

The positive but non-significant relationship between innovation capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 2.259483, p-value = 0.0668) suggests that innovation efforts may contribute to firm value, but the impact is not substantial enough to be statistically significant. Innovation capital, which encompasses the knowledge, ideas, and innovations that firms generate, is a critical component of intellectual capital. The finding implies that while innovation efforts may be beneficial for firms, they may not necessarily lead to significant increases in market value. This may be due to various factors, such as the high costs associated with innovation, the uncertainty of innovation outcomes, or the lack of effective commercialization strategies. The finding highlights the need for industrial goods firms in Nigeria to carefully evaluate the

costs and benefits of innovation efforts and to develop effective strategies for commercializing innovations.

The positive but non-significant relationship between innovation capital and price-to-book value is consistent with some previous studies. While Aljuboori et al. (2022) found that innovation capability mediates the relationship between intellectual capital and firm performance, other studies have reported mixed results or insignificant relationships between innovation capital and firm performance.

4.4.5 Process capital and price-to-book value

The negative but non-significant relationship between process capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = -0.0271887, p-value = 0.0893) suggests that process inefficiencies or ineffective process management may not significantly detract from firm value, but may still require attention to optimize firm performance. Process capital, which encompasses the processes and systems that firms use to create and deliver value, is a critical component of intellectual capital. The finding implies that while process capital may not be a significant driver of firm value, it is still essential for firms to optimize their processes and systems to achieve operational efficiency and effectiveness. This is consistent with the operations management literature, which emphasizes the importance of process optimization and continuous improvement in driving firm performance. The finding highlights the need for industrial goods firms in Nigeria to prioritize process optimization and continuous improvement to enhance their operational efficiency and effectiveness. The negative but non-significant relationship between process capital and price-to-book value is consistent with some previous studies that have reported mixed results or insignificant relationships between process capital and firm performance. This is however an avenue for further studies in this area by other researchers.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of findings

This present study examined the relationship between intellectual capital and fair value of industrial good firms listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). The independent variable (intellectual capital) was proxied by human capital, structural capital, relational capital, innovation capital and process capital while the dependent variable (fair value) was proxied by price-to-book value. The study covered ten (10)-year period (2015-2024). Below is a summary of findings gathered through a panel multiple regression analysis.

1. There is significant positive relationship between human capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 1.280405{0.0001}) of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
2. There is a significant positive relationship between structural capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 4.128763{0.0000}) of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
3. There is a significant positive relationship between relational capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 0.529721 {0.0025}) of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
4. There is a positive non-significant relationship between innovation capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = 2.259483{0.0668}) of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
5. There is a negative non-significant relationship between process capital and price-to-book value (Coeff. = -0.0271887{0.0893}) of listed Industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

This study provides valuable insights into the relationship between intellectual capital and fair value of industrial goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The findings suggest that human capital, structural capital, and relational capital are significant drivers of firm value, as proxied by price-to-book value. The positive and significant relationships between these components of intellectual capital and firm value highlight the importance of investing in and leveraging these assets to enhance firm performance and competitiveness. The results of this study have implications for industrial goods firms in Nigeria, suggesting that they should prioritize investments in human capital, structural capital, and relational capital to improve their market value and competitiveness.

The study's findings also highlight areas for further improvement. The positive but non-significant relationship between innovation capital and firm value suggests that while innovation efforts may be beneficial, they may not necessarily lead to significant increases in market value. Similarly, the negative but non-significant relationship between process capital and firm value suggests that process inefficiencies or ineffective process management may not significantly detract from firm value, but may still require attention to optimize firm performance. It is thus concluded that intellectual capital, particularly human capital, structural capital, and relational capital, plays a vital role in driving firm value of industrial goods firms in Nigeria. As such, firms should prioritize investments in these areas to enhance their competitiveness and market value.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations should be adhered to:

1. Industrial goods firms in Nigeria should prioritize investments in human capital development, such as training and development programs, talent acquisition and retention, and employee empowerment.
2. Firms should focus on building and maintaining effective organizational structures and systems to drive firm performance and value.'
3. Companies should prioritize building and maintaining strong relationships with stakeholders, including customers, suppliers, and partners.
4. Firms should continue to prioritize innovation efforts, such as research and development, product innovation, and process innovation, to stay competitive and adapt to changing market conditions.
5. Firms should focus on optimizing their processes and systems to achieve operational efficiency and effectiveness, such as through process automation, lean manufacturing, and continuous improvement initiatives.

5.4 Contribution to knowledge

1. The study provides empirical evidence of the significant positive relationship between intellectual capital (human capital, structural capital, and relational capital) and firm value (price-to-book value) in the context of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
2. The study highlights the relative importance of different components of intellectual capital, with structural capital having the largest coefficient followed by human capital and relational capital.
3. The study provides insights into the intellectual capital-firm value relationship in the Nigerian industrial goods sector, which may be useful for firms operating in similar contexts.
4. The study suggests that innovation capital may not have a significant impact on firm value in the short term, but may still be important for long-term sustainability and competitiveness.
5. The study identifies process capital as an area for improvement, given its negative non-significant relationship with firm value, highlighting the need for firms to optimize their processes and systems to achieve operational efficiency and effectiveness.

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